

CRAFT AND FAITH-BASED SOUVENIRS

THE CASE OF TWO CITIES IN TURKEY

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ABSTRACT

Souvenirs are reminders that indicate a particular time, location or attraction and are generally associated with a touristic act or a ceremony. The tourism potential of a province is supported by a souvenir market in which the local identity is commercialized. This paper presents a comparative study of the souvenir market in two touristic locations in Turkey, namely Hacibektas and Konya, particular for their belief tourism. These two destinations are known for their lodges and they attract a considerable number of tourists, both domestic and international. Souvenirs from a sacred place are expected to reflect its sacredness. This secret characteristic is associated with a local underground resource and craft in Hacibektas, while Konya is known as an industrial center as well. The aim of the study is to scrutinize the motives behind small scale faith-based souvenir production, and its relationship with craft.

KEYWORDS: *souvenir, design, faith, craft, belief tourism.*

INTRODUCTION

The recent souvenir market demonstrates conventional patterns of products in nearly every tourist destination. Although souvenirs are expected to reflect the local identity with local production patterns, indigenous sources and local indicators, they can be found far away from where they were produced. Traditional crafts appear to reflect local identity as they depend on native resources. Craft also operates as a means to sanctify a gift. For this reason, craft oriented souvenirs are respected as intimate pieces transferring the soul of their places of origin.

The paper aims to investigate the condition of the souvenir market and the place of craft items in two Turkish destinations particularly known for belief tourism, namely Hacibektas and Konya. These two centers are known for having been the dwelling places of two holy persons whose dates and places of birth—Persia—were close, and both of whom migrated to Anatolia as a result of the Mongolian conquests. The lodges founded by these two saints hosted craft guilds particular to the regions. The stone guild of Hacibektas and felt guild of Konya gave rise to a certain tradition, which lasted until recently. This study aims to make a comparison between these two cities with respect to the local conditions and touristic potential.

THE SOUVENIR AS A DISTINCT PRODUCT CATEGORY

Culture is bundled up with business services, leisure industries and tourism in an effort to regenerate city-regions and therefore create wealth and employment (Booth and Boyle, 1993 referred by Julier, 2008). While cultural industries contribute to the identity of a space by creating a more dynamic, creative and enterprising population, they also provide the designer with a dynamic status in the entrepreneurial culture. Designers, as the signifiers of modernity, contribute to an urban center's national and international promotion with their skills in participating in commercial networks and technical know-how (Julier, 2008). The design act carried out for such a promotion involves graphics, items and services for tourists in general. Souvenirs appear as the particular items created for those tourists.

Souvenirs are reminders of a particular time, location or attraction and are generally associated with a touristic act or a ceremony. These generally unbranded items appear as a unique product category that operate as agents that commoditize a province. According to Gordon, souvenirs are classified as "pictorial images" such as postcards; "pieces of the rock" such as sea shells collected from nature; "symbolic shorthand"

such as the icons particular to any space that, in time, were turned into mass produced gadgets, "markers" like the printed t-shirts and "local products" whose material and production are indigenous to the area (1986). The important attributes of souvenirs are product value (range, quality), product display characteristics (color, display, packaging, size), and uniqueness (Turner, Reisinger, 2001). However, the expanding interest in such unique pieces brings together the increase in production and popularization that lead to decreased authenticity.

Tourism is an economic act, which emerged with the need to travel in order to seek out new experiences and ways of life. The tourists who experience alienation through their daily working lives pursue authenticity through their journeys and holidays to return home with an experience of a more primitive or alternative lifestyle (Litrell, Anderson, Brown, 1993). The authentic experience of this alternative lifestyle is identified and carried to real life via the souvenirs. The term authenticity is generally taken as a concept of reproduction of the realness belonging to the other. It is a conceptualization of an elusive, inadequately defined, other cultural, socially ordered genuineness (Spooner, 1986). Authenticity is a socially constructed interpretation of the realness of the objects. Namely, authentic experiences come from constructed reality by beliefs, attitudes and powers, not from inherent realness (Cohen, 1988). Authenticity is regarded as a child of old-fashioned exoticism using the forms and styles of a supposedly homogenous and unbroken tradition (Rushdie, 1991, as cited by Taylor, 2001: 7).

Time spent during the visit to sacred spaces is regarded to be sacred too. Accordingly, the souvenirs bought during these visits are also regarded as sacred. These souvenirs also operate as tools to strengthen traditional religious practices. As items particular to faith-based design, these objects are either traditional items used in religious rituals, or items onto which faith-specific ornaments, slogans or forms are applied (Gorman, 2009). While handwork operates as the tool to sanctify a gift (Belk et.al, 1989), traditional crafts become one of the primary components in sacred souvenirs. Moreover, as a reminder of a trip to a holy place, craft based souvenirs are regarded as being much more holy. But the fact is that the souvenir market is dominated by mass-produced cheap items, in general, due to the high cost of craft based production or the disappearance of traditional crafts.

TWO CENTERS FOR BELIEF TOURISM

In order to trace the impact of craft on the souvenir market in holy places, two towns in Turkey particular for belief tourism were selected. In these two towns, there are two lodges that serve as the centers for two sects specific to Anatolia. These two lodges were founded on relatively close dates and by two saints Haji Bektash-i Veli and Mawlana Jalaaladdin-i Rumi. Born on dates and cities—in Khorasan, Persia—close to each other, they both migrated to Anatolia escaping from the Mongolian conquests. The doctrine of these two saints formed the two roots in morality of the Anatolian population. Moreover, traditional Turkish music is said to be rooted in the music

of these two sects: Bektashi music is regarded as the origin of Turkish folk music, whereas Mewlevi music is the base of traditional classical Turkish music. These two lodges are located in Hacibektas (a town belonging to the city of Nevsehir) and Konya. After the foundation of the Turkish Republic, all of the lodges were closed and today the aforementioned lodges serve as museums.

Hacibektas

Hacibektas is a town in the city of Nevsehir, with a population of 11.700. As a typical central Anatolian town, the source of income is generally agriculture and stockbreeding. Onyx mining used to be one of the main branches of business, but this has been discontinued over the last 20 years. Stonework is also linked with Bektashi mythology and the first stone guild is said to be founded in the Bektashi lodge.

Haji Bektash-i Veli, the founder of the Bektashi lodge in this town, was born in 1209 in Nishapur of Khorasan, Persia and died in 1271 in Hacibektas. With the impact of the Mongolian conquests in the region, he migrated to Anatolia and settled in Sulucakarahoyuk, which was then given the name Hacibektas. His doctrine is regarded to have adapted the Shamanic Turkic belief system to Islam with certain respect for nature.

Recently, the region's potential for tourism has been supported by Cappadocia: a near-by tourist destination and a sacred site for Christians. Every year commemoration ceremonies are held in August for Haji Bektash-i Veli. The lodge, which is turned into a museum, is visited by 450.000 tourists every year and 10.000 of them are international tourists that stopover in Cappadocia (interview with Taylan Sümer, 2013). Today, Hacibektas is one of the destinations visited in Cappadocia tours. However, the meaning of the province changes for domestic and international tourists. For international tourists, Hacibektas is a minor destination visited in only a few hours. For domestic tourists, however, the province is the primary destination visited by faith tourists.

Konya

Konya, the capital of the Anatolian Seljuk state between 1076-1277, is known today as an agriculture and industry center and one of the important destinations for belief tourism. The city center with a population of 1.100.000 is the 7th largest city in Turkey and together with its counties has the largest area survey.

As a center for belief tourism, the city is known for the Mewlevi lodge founded by Mawlana Jalaladdin Rumi. Mawlana was born in 1207 in Belkh, Khorasan, Persia and passed away in 1273 in Konya. Similar to Haci Bektash, he left Khorasan because of the Mongolian conquests and settled in the Seljuk capital Konya with his father, one of the era's eminent mutasavvifs. After his father's demise, Mawlana filled in for him and built a remarkable reputation as a person of knowledge and wisdom (Efe, 2013).

Every year, in memory of Mawlana, vuslat ceremonies are held on the 17th of December, the date Mawlana passed away. The

lodge welcomes about 2.000.000 visitors a year and about 1.500.000 of them are domestic tourists (interview with Yasar Sarican, 2014).

SOUVENIR, CRAFT AND BELIEF TOURISM

Recent state of the market

As destinations particular for belief tourism, both Hacibektas and Konya have a marketplace for souvenir items. The market is dominated by symbolic shorthand and local products whose production is not limited to the region. Moreover, some items are imported goods produced in China or Afghanistan as demanded by the local market.

The difference in scale of these two cities is very much reflected in the souvenir market of both. As a small town with a population of about 12.000, and with a 450.000 visitors a year, Hacibektas has a modest market which mainly depends on stonework. In that sense, the range of products is homogeneous with respect to the range in Konya. As an industrial zone, Konya is able to operate international contacts and host diverse production activities ranging from the food industry to plastics. As a reflection of such a vibrant medium, the souvenir market in Konya does not reflect a homogenous craft based character. The craft items are diversified, local products come from different parts of Turkey, and Chinese low-cost products appear as a strong competitor to the local products.

Craftwork in Hacibektas is limited to stonework and has thus allowed stonework to become one of the markers of the region. The local resource, namely onyx stone, refers to Shamanic Turkish mythology as well as the Bektashi faith. As an extension of the mountain cult in shaman-Turkish mythology, stone is regarded to be sacred and is transformed into a symbol of the homeland. At the same time, and as a part of the feminine asset of the Turkic-shaman mountain cult, it became the symbol of fertility. The mountain, as the axis guarding the balance of the world, and the place nearest to God, was believed to engulf the sun every evening and give birth to it again on every morning. The ageless mythological asset called Babal, the possessor of the stones, is regarded to be another component of the stone cult. Babal is believed to reserve a weightless and invisible stone for each newborn to hang around its neck. As the infant grows up and dies, the stone falls from his neck. Anyone who finds this stone is believed to live long and know everything (Bayat, 2007).

Onyx accessories such as the stone of surrender and kanberiyye were eminent components of Bektashi dervish attire (figure 1). Today, these components have been turned into souvenirs to an extent; however, they do not dominate the whole market. Onyx items for daily use such as candleholders or other tabletop objects are very common in the souvenir market (figure 2). Rather than shaping the item around religion, the faith content is attached to products by applying motives particular to the Bektashi faith. Some calligraphic depictions are applied onto the selected items by the souvenir shop owners on customer

Figure 1. Bektashi dervish attire with stone of surrender, pahleng and kanberiyye

Figure 2. Onyx items

demand during purchase (figure 3). Some products seem to have been stripped of their faith-based content and made into decorative items. For example, the elliptic "kanberiyye" stone, which is a part of the dervish attire, was turned into an onyx egg to refer to the stone's symbol of fertility (figure 4). Other faith-based depictions are observed to be produced as accessories that are minimized in size (figure 5).

Other than onyx items, the market welcomes pictorial images, holograms, silver accessories and carpets. The local onyx

Figure 3. Calligraphy applied on onyx plate

products were distributed to other tourist-destination provinces of Turkey about 35 years ago. However, the increasing production costs resulted in a decrease in mining and production (Akbulut, 2013).

The market in Konya offers a diverse range of souvenirs, which—as a result of the varied modes of production and access to business relations—can be imported and produced locally. The main crafts are felt making and ceramics and reed flute making and wood painting are also popular. Reed flutes are used particularly in Mewlevi music. On the other hand, the wooden spoons decorated with Mewlevi figures such as whirling dervishes or the lodge operate as the pictorial images (figure 6).

Felt and ceramic items appear to be dominant craft pieces in the market. Ceramics are either from domestic or Chinese producers (figure 7). Beginning in 2003, knickknacks in the shape of whirling dervishes began to be imported from China and these low-cost figures with slanting eyes invaded the market. There are also abstract dervish figures made by ceramic artists settled in Konya (figure 8).

There are unique pieces to be found in felt making also. Felt refers back to nomadic Turkish tradition and Mewlevi philosophy. Similar to Bektashi dervish attire, felt caps are indispensable components of Mewlevi dervish attire (figure 9). While traditional production methods have changed over the past 20 years, the products varied and the craft gained currency.

Figure 4. Onyx eggs inspired from kanberiyeye of dervish attire

Figure 5. Faith-based depictions turned into accessories

The range of felt souvenirs varies from accessories (necklace, fibula, handbag, purse, scarf), to garments (hats, jackets), to parts of dervish attire (sikke or caps) (figure 10) and decorative items (wall panels, covers) (figure 11).

Besides ceramics, Chinese products include mechanical items. The whirling dervish is a characteristic form for Konya and is very much used in music boxes and clocks (figure 12). Such items provide a fair like atmosphere to the souvenir market with their sound and kinetic images.

Figure 6. decorated wooden spoons

Figure 7. Ceramic knickknacks in the form of whirling dervishes, from China. Glass varieties in the middle row.

Figure 8. Some examples of local ceramics

Figure 9. Mewlevi dervish attire

Figure 10. Felt mini-cap production in workshop

Figure 11. Felt items

Figure 12. Clocks with whirling dervish

Master's attachment

In the case of belief tourism, craft is generally linked with a province's natural resources. Especially in the case of Hacibektas and Konya, craft is linked spiritually to the lodges. In Hacibektas, the stone guild, and in Konya the felt guild were first founded in the lodges. Both of the crafts and materials (stone and felt) are linked with the belief system and few remaining masters are still sentimentally attached to the order of the lodge.

The craft masters interviewed appear to be born into crafts families and trained by relatives. The craft descends from father to son. However, due to the financial circumstances, the masters appear to alternate between other means of income generation at some stages of their lives. However, this does not mean a total separation from the craft. After trying other occupations, some return to the craft or the craft becomes a side occupation alongside a job providing stable income. For example, Hüseyin Gökçe, a former stonemaster who is cur-

rently an officer in museum in Hacibektas, switches to craft-work, at a particular time of year in order to help his family's small scale souvenir production for the ceremonies in August.

The craftsmen generally experience tension between creative self-expression and the need to conform to societal demands and financial realism (Ranson, 1989). The interviewed masters are found to be involved with the production of traditional items at the beginning such as felt covers, dervish caps or stones of surrender. Today, these masters appear not to follow classical patterns of production due to the changing market conditions. First of all, the classical items that were produced by the fathers of these masters are generally of no use today. Traditionally, felt is used to make covers for the traditional sofas called *divan*, or the *shakedown*s, or as *shepherds'* garments. Felt master Celallettin Berberoğlu started making felt with his grandfather and father by making such kind of items. In the 1990s, he decided to search for alternative ways of using the fabric and therefore began making souvenirs such as pendants, scarves, and other decorative items. Today, he also runs a felt training program in his workshop. The stonemaster Deniz Ulutaş in Hacibektas, shifted to gravestone and workbench production because of the souvenir market's low profit margins. However, his family is known to be the leading souvenir producer in the town.

The masters are very much involved with the mystic content of the craft and the material. Felt, for example, is a reflection of the Mewlevi understanding of the human being according to Celallettin Berberoğlu, who is a whirling dervish at the same time:

"... wool and the human being are both going through a process of purification. The wool must be lambswool, not the sheep's, and it should meet with a piece of water in order to become felt. The master kneads that wool in a straw mat. Then, the master flattens the wool under his feet with the same rhythmic breathing and pronouncing the sound "huh". Actually, hu is the manifestation of God, and what is being stamped on is the ego of the human being, everything that we are not but we thing we are; status, money, fame, everything. The master is the mentor and he knows the state of the wool in the mat without seeing it. And when the mat is opened, we meet with a texture that shrunken. The shrunken element becomes firmer, the one behaving modestly, grows..." (2014)

Moreover, the traditional forms with religious content are regarded to be immune elements whose production should be restricted to the region. In the souvenir market in Hacibektas, most of the items appear to be produced in Afghanistan where production costs are minimal. However, religious forms such as the surrender stone are still made in the town. Deniz Ulutaş, the stone master, strongly opposes the idea of carrying the production of the surrender stone to Afghanistan:

"... The Afghan knows nothing about the stone of surrender, no, they cannot make it." (2013)

The question of authenticity

Craft is an element that transfers the holiness of a place to its souvenirs. It is also a manifestation of authenticity in souve-

nirs for tourists. Objective authenticity can be defined as an experience which genuinely samples the culture of the other; that is, the host society and the host people (Hillman, 2012:2). As typical tourists' travel motivations include such things as social status, cultural enrichment, and learning new things, experiencing a foreign destination successfully works with such souvenirs that remind people of their trips (Swanson, Horridge, 2006).

However, objects are not the sole elements that transfer authenticity; this can also be done through shows and hands on experiences. The question is whether these "staged experiences" supported by a "staged authenticity" meet with the tourists' motivation for genuine, spontaneous and authentic experience and to see real life as it is. The artificial settings created for the tourists serve as a front stage where a 'false reality' for show and performance is constructed (Hillman, 2012). As a result, the souvenirs appear as the reminders of these staged experiences created through staged authenticity.

In both cases, the tourists are provided with a holy dance show: *semah* in Hacibektas and *sema* in Konya. For destinations peculiar for belief tourism, craft does not appear as a primary attraction, but the craft's link with the belief is generally provided with the souvenir items. These items are generally components of the dervish attire: the stone of surrender in Hacibektas and the felt *sikke* (cap) in Konya, the material is attributed mystic characteristics.

The souvenirs that are originally parts of dervish attire, such as surrender stones or dervish caps, can be regarded as elements of staged authenticity. The tourist purchasing such items will not be involved in a religious act involving the items, but the items are kept as the reminders of the trip and the holy nature of the region. This holy characteristic is transferred to other souvenirs for daily use with the craft or the material specific to the region. For example, the holy stone is used to make sugar bowls, ashtrays, candleholders, etc. or the lodge's craft, namely felt making, is popular in textile and accessory production.

Augmenting the province's touristic potential with hands-on craft shows is a hot debate in Hacibektas. In Cappadocia, which is a popular touristic destination close to Hacibektas, the tourists are provided with a ceramic production experience in which they are able to sit on a turn bench and play with mud. The stone masters in Hacibektas tend to adapt such an experience to stone workshops in order to attract more tourists and to resurrect the production of stone items in the region.

Authenticity in such regions is impaired by the transgression of certain items peculiar to certain places. One of the well-known souvenirs of Konya is the bergamot-flavored candy known as *Mewlana* candy. Recently, this item is also being produced as "Hacibektas candy" and sold in the Hacibektas souvenir market (Figure 13). Another example is that of rose scented beads produced in Isparta (Figure 14). Such items with religious references can hold a place in the souvenir market without the need to be authentic.

Figure 13. Transgressive candy

CONCLUSION

Craft, as the local production act depending on indigenous resources, is a particular element for the souvenir market in tourist sites. The authenticity of a souvenir is very much supported by local businesses and crafts. It occupies a particular place in belief tourism as craftwork is regarded to be the sole element to sanctify a gift. However, it is not supported much by the souvenir market and high production costs and the decreasing number of craft masters forces the market to shift to mass produced and even kitsch items.

The selected regions were particular for belief tourism with lodges particular to craft guilds. The souvenir markets in these regions are studied with respect to the craft activity particular to the regions and the lodges. As a matter of fact, the souvenir market is observed to present a false reality in either craft based items or mass-produced ones.

The faith origin of the craft and the material is hardly recognizable in the market. Although the craft masters are sentimentally attached to their belief, they hardly survive with traditional modes of production and are forced to shift alternative modes or sources of income. The souvenir market appears as a means for the craft to survive, but the false reality of the souvenir embraces the danger of breeding corrupt variations of traditional forms. On the other hand, the traditional faith based forms are generally observed to be miniaturized and rendered into functional items or accessories such as necklaces, key rings etc. So the belief content is transformed into daily life.

Intense industry in Konya is reflected in the souvenir market by inhibiting it from demonstrating a craft based character. The souvenirs are from different cities, countries, materials and origins. In such a circumstance, the souvenir market is dominated by certain forms of whirling dervishes, the depictions of the Mevlevi lodge or calligraphic pieces. On the other hand, the scarcity of resources in Hacibektas results in a modest and homogenous market dominated by onyx items. However this homogenous structure offers a void market behind it; the production act together with the source of onyx is partly based in the town.

Figure 14. Scented beads of Isparta in Konya souvenir shops

Unfortunately, the traditional crafts are about to disappear. It is not easy for the few remaining masters to find apprentices to take over the craft. The education programs offered by public training centers cannot survive due to lack of interest. As felt is a textile-based material, it has recently become popular among women. Stonework, on the other hand, is scarce given that it requires heavy machinery and raw material. Certain models such as hands on craft practice shows are thought to be adapted to rejuvenate stone mastery in the region. Another way to raise interest in craft can be through publicity as it can act to emphasize the crafts' faith based origin. Linking the material and craft with the spirituality of the region enhances awareness and results in a souvenir market without corruption.

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